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Two constructed wetlands within a Mediterranean natural park immersed in an agrolandscape reduce most heavy metal water concentrations and dampen the majority of pesticide presence

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Corresponding Author:	Maria A. Rodrigo, Dr. Universitat de Valencia SPAIN	
Corresponding Author Secondary Information:		
Corresponding Author's Institution:	Universitat de Valencia	
Corresponding Author's Secondary Institution:		
First Author:	Maria A. Rodrigo, Dr.	
First Author Secondary Information:		
Order of Authors:	Maria A. Rodrigo, Dr. Eric Puche, Dr. Nuria Carabal Sergio Armenta, Dr. Francesc A. Esteve-Turrillas, Dr. Javier Jiménez Fernando Juan	
Order of Authors Secondary Information:		
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Abstract:	<p>The water concentrations of 12 heavy and other metals/metalloids were analysed seasonally along two horizontal-flow constructed wetlands -CWs- (Tancat Mília -TM- and Tancat l'Illa -TLI) located within the Mediterranean Albufera de València Natural Park during 2020-2021. A wide-scope screening of pesticides present in waters was also performed. The two CWs were created to improve water quality and increase biodiversity. They currently receive effluent waters from two different tertiary-treatment wastewater plants, and the water flows along the CWs before being discharged into the main lagoon and a smaller lagoon in TM and TLI, respectively. TLI manages to reduce (Mn) or maintain the concentration of most of the studied elements (Zn, Ni, Hg, Cr, Fe Cd, Cu) at the same level as outside (67%). Only Al, Pb, B and As remain at a higher concentration. TM also reduces Zn and Cu and keeps the concentration of Cr, Cd and Hg (representing 42%). Al, Pb, B and As remain at higher concentrations, as in TLI, but Ni, Fe and Mn are also at higher concentrations. Although both CWs vary in their ability to remove elements, no risks to human health or the environment have been detected due to the low metal concentration in their outlets, all of them (except Hg) below the legal limits for environmental quality in the European Union. With the detection of 71</p>	

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1 **Two constructed wetlands within a Mediterranean natural park immersed in an**
2 **agrolandscape reduce most heavy metal water concentrations and dampen the**
3 **majority of pesticide presence**

4 Maria A. Rodrigo^{1*}, Eric Puche¹, Nuria Carabal¹, Sergio Armenta², Francesc A. Esteve-Turrillas², Javier
5 Jiménez³ and Fernando Juan⁴

6 ¹Integrative Ecology Group. Cavanilles Institute of Biodiversity and Evolutionary Biology, University of
7 València. Catedrático José Beltrán 2, E-46980, Paterna, Spain. Telephone: Int+34963543596

8 ²Department of Analytical Chemistry. University of Valencia. Dr Moliner 50, E-46100, Burjassot, Spain

9 ³Hidraqua Gestión Integral de Aguas de Levante, S.A. Carrer de Sant Sebastià, 12, E-46910 Alfafar,
10 Valencia, Spain

11 ⁴Aguas de las Cuencas Mediterráneas, S.A. (ACUAMED). Pasaje Doctor Serra 2, 3º planta, E-46004,
12 Valencia, Spain

13 *Corresponding author: Maria A. Rodrigo (maria.a.rodrigo@uv.es)

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16

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25

26 **Abstract**

27 The water concentrations of 12 heavy and other metals/metalloids were analysed seasonally along two
28 horizontal-flow constructed wetlands -CWs- (Tancat Mília -TM- and Tancat l'Illa -TLI) located within
29 the Mediterranean *Albufera de València* Natural Park during 2020-2021. A wide-scope screening of
30 pesticides present in waters was also performed. The two CWs were created to improve water quality and
31 increase biodiversity. They currently receive effluent waters from two different tertiary-treatment
32 wastewater plants, and the water flows along the CWs before being discharged into the main lagoon and a
33 smaller lagoon in TM and TLI, respectively. TLI manages to reduce (Mn) or maintain the concentration
34 of most of the studied elements (Zn, Ni, Hg, Cr, Fe Cd, Cu) at the same level as outside (67%). Only Al,
35 Pb, B and As remain at a higher concentration. TM also reduces Zn and Cu and keeps the concentration
36 of Cr, Cd and Hg (representing 42%). Al, Pb, B and As remain at higher concentrations, as in TLI, but Ni,
37 Fe and Mn are also at higher concentrations. Although both CWs vary in their ability to remove elements,
38 no risks to human health or the environment have been detected due to the low metal concentration in
39 their outlets, all of them (except Hg) below the legal limits for environmental quality in the European
40 Union. With the detection of 71 compounds in water in each CW area (26 herbicides, 26 insecticides and
41 19 fungicides in TLI, and 29 herbicides, 23 insecticides and 19 fungicides in TM), we also provide
42 evidence of the impact of pesticides, which depends on the application method (helicopter, tractor),
43 originated from areas with high agricultural pressure (chiefly rice crops) on systems (mainly TM) created
44 to preserve biodiversity. Nevertheless, both systems provide crucial environmental services in water
45 quality in this agrolandscape.

46

47 **Keywords:** Domestic wastewater; Tertiary treatment; Metals/Metalloids; Herbicides; Fungicides;
48 Insecticides; Rice agriculture

49

50 **Introduction**

51 Constructed wetlands (CWs) as ecological and alternative solutions for wastewater treatment have proven
52 effective worldwide, particularly for nutrient reduction (Kadlec and Wallace 2008). However, the studies
53 on CWs being used to reduce other kinds of pollution, such as priority hazardous substances, from
54 municipal wastewater treatment plants before being discharged into natural and protected areas are scarce
55 (Arroyo et al. 2010; Pedescoll et al. 2015). Wastewater, even treated, may contain undesirable chemical
56 constituents such as heavy metals and pesticides, particularly in highly populated areas with intensive
57 agricultural activities, such as coastal areas in the Mediterranean. The presence of both kind of substances
58 can be related, since, for example, fertilizers are usually not sufficiently purified during the manufacturing
59 processes, for economic reasons, and usually contain several impurities, including heavy metals.
60 Moreover, heavy metals often form a part of the active compounds of pesticides (Gimeno-García et al.
61 1996). Many other human activities introduce metals into the environment (e.g., mining, traffic,
62 industries, wastewater treatment plants, waste landfills, etc.) (Hernández-Crespo and Martín, 2015).
63 Moreover, tertiary treatments in wastewater treatment plants using chemical reagents (coagulants,
64 flocculants, etc.) to increase the removal efficiency of phosphorus and other nutrients (Iborra-Clar et al.
65 2011), may represent a source of certain elements being discharged into sensitive ecosystems such as
66 wetlands within natural parks.

67 The global term “heavy metals” sometimes includes other elements belonging to the periodical system,
68 which are in fact not metals (e.g., boron), nor are they “heavy” (e.g., aluminium, manganese, iron), but
69 they can become a serious environmental problem (e.g., acute and chronic toxicity to aquatic organisms,
70 accumulation in the ecosystem and losses of habitats and biodiversity; Directive 2008/105/EC; Yu et al.
71 2021). Within the term pesticide, a broader spectrum of substances is included, such as herbicides,
72 insecticides, fungicides, but also repellents, growth regulators, etc. (European Commission, 2020).
73 Pesticides are considered as pollutants by the Water Framework Directive (WFD, Directive,
74 2000/60/EEC), and are considered priority substances by Directive 2013/39/EU, being categorized as
75 dangerous substances by Directive 2006/11/EC. In fact, monitoring studies have reported the presence of
76 a large number of these types of contaminants in water bodies across Europe (Houtman 2010; Hedge et
77 al. 2014; Rico et al. 2016; Rico et al. 2019). Furthermore, this chemical pollution is highly related and
78 affects some other water quality parameters, depicting a complex amalgam of factors which have to be
79 taken into consideration (Rico et al. 2016).

80 The *Albufera de València* Natural Park is one of the most important wetlands in the Iberian Peninsula and
81 the Mediterranean zone: it has been protected by the Ramsar Convention on Wetlands since 1990;
82 mentioned as a special protection area (SPA) by the Birds Directive (Directive 2009/147/EC) since 1991;
83 included in the Natura 2000 network (MITECO, 2021) as well as being classified as a Site of Community
84 Importance (SCI) by the Habitat Directive (Council Directive 92/43/EEC) in 2006. However, currently,
85 the area is still subjected to degradation, which started at the beginning of the 1970s (Dafauce 1975).
86 Intensive agriculture, urbanization and industrial activities are the main causes of said deterioration (Soria
87 2006). For example, metals such as iron, zinc and copper have been applied to rice-growing soils in the
88 form of pesticides at levels of 1–15 kg/ha per year, whereas cadmium has been applied in fertilizers at
89 amounts of 150–450 mg/ha per year (Boluda et al. 1993).

90 Among the several initiatives implemented within the *Albufera de València* Natural Park to reduce water
91 pollution, one of them is the construction of the above mentioned CWs surrounding the main lagoon
92 (called the *Albufera de València*) (Martín et al. 2013; Rodrigo et al. 2013). These CWs were created from
93 the transformation of former rice fields. These artificial wetlands were also constructed to recover lost
94 habitats in the natural park they belong to, so as to improve biodiversity both inside and outside the CWs
95 (Hernández-Crespo et al. 2017; Rodrigo and Segura 2020). Two of these CWs are located south of the
96 main lagoon, and currently are exclusively fed by the effluents of two wastewater treatment plants.
97 Moreover, the CWs are immersed in a landscape devoted mainly to rice agriculture, where pesticide
98 treatments were and continue to be applied (Calvo et al. 2021).

99 Several studies of heavy metals and pesticides in the aquatic habitats of the *Albufera de València* Natural
100 Park have been carried out (see Gimeno-García et al. 1996 for the first and Calvo et al. 2021, and
101 references therein, for the latter). However, the performance of the CWs within this Natural Park in
102 relation to heavy metals and pesticides has never been approached. Thus, the aim of this study is to assess
103 how the wastewater effluents, as water supply to the CWs, impact on the changes in the concentrations of
104 said elements and compounds as water passes through these systems. We hypothesize that most
105 elements/compound concentrations in the inlets will be reduced, while others may be increased and this
106 will depend on the type of inputs and on the biological, physical and chemical processes acting within the
107 different sectors of the CWs (presence/absence of vegetation, type of vegetation, accumulation of humic
108 substances, etc.).

109 **Material and methods**

110 *Study sites*

111 Tancat de Mília (TM hereafter) and Tancat de l'Illa (TLI hereafter) are two CWs located to the south of
112 the *Albufera de València* lagoon within the natural park (Fig. 1a). In this natural park there are 21,000 ha
113 devoted to the cultivation of rice. The TM (33.4 ha) and TLI (16 ha) CWs were formerly rice fields and
114 were transformed into CWs in 2011. Both CWs have several sectors of surface-flow water (*B* sectors) and
115 a shallow lagoon located at the end of the system (sector *C*). Moreover, TM has a sector of horizontal
116 subsurface flow (sector *A*) at the beginning of the area (Fig. 1a). Since the middle of 2019, the incoming
117 waters in both CWs have been the effluents of two sewage water treatment plants (SWTP) with tertiary
118 treatment (*Albufera Sur* SWTP in the case of TM and *Sueca* SWTP in the case of TLI). The water flows
119 from the inlet to sector *A* (only in TM), then pass to the *B* sectors and finally to sector *C*. After passing
120 through the CWs, the water is returned to the *Albufera de València* lagoon, in the case of TM, and to a
121 small lagoon that drains the irrigation water from the surrounding rice fields (*Estany de la Plana*) in the
122 case of TLI. The mean water depth range is 30-60 cm in TLI, and 10-45 cm in TM. The laminar flow is
123 960 m³/day for TLI and 1400 m³/day for TM. Global hydraulic retention time is ca. 30 days (Hernández-
124 Crespo et al. 2017; Martín-Monerris and Hernández-Crespo, pers. comm.).

125 The *B* sectors in both CWs are planted with emergent plants (mainly *Phragmites* spp., *Typha* spp., but
126 also *Cladium mariscus*, *Scirpus* spp., *Juncus* spp., *Iris pseudacorus*; semiaquatic or amphibian plants
127 such as *Lithrum salicaria*, *Kosteletzkya pentacarpos* and *Hydrocotyle vulgaris* are also found). In TLI
128 there is a predominance of *Typha* spp., and in TM *Phragmites australis* is the most abundant species
129 followed by *Typha* spp. In sector *C*, submerged vegetation, composed of *Myriophyllum spicatum*, *Najas*
130 *marina*, *Ceratophyllum demersum* and *C. submersum* developed in TLI, forming an extensive coverage in
131 September 2021. *Potamogeton nodosus* and *Stuckenia pectinata* had been present, but were no longer
132 detected. However, sector *C* in TM remained with no submerged vegetation throughout the sampled
133 period. For further details on the study sites see Hernández-Crespo et al. (2017) and Rodrigo and Segura
134 (2020).

135 *Sample collection and analytical procedures*

136 Three water samples were collected (at a depth of 0.2 m) within each CW, and one sample was taken
137 outside the CWs for inside-outside comparison (Fig. 1a). The samples within the CWs were taken at the

138 start of the system (the first part of the *B* sectors; sites I1 and M1 for TLI and TM, respectively), in the
139 middle part of the *B* sectors (sites I2 and M2) and at the end of the system (sector *C*; site I3 and M3). The
140 outside samples (sites “Out”) were taken in the *Estany de la Plana* lagoon in the case of TLI, and in a
141 channel surrounding the TM CW where rice fields drain. The sampling data was mainly selected
142 according to the representative months of the rice cultivation period (Fig. 1b) from September 2020 to
143 September 2021, since the area is clearly affected by aerial and terrestrial pesticide treatment (Gamón et
144 al. 2003; Gómez de Barreda Ferraz et al. 2004; Calvo et al. 2021) which occurs at the beginning of the
145 cultivation (May), in the middle of the pesticide treatment (July) and before harvesting (September).
146 Furthermore, samples were also taken in February and March, during the dry period. In TM, an extra
147 sample was taken in late summer 2021 at the entrance of sector *A* (M0). This made up a total of 24
148 samples for TLI and 25 for TM. After collection, water samples were transported in a portable freezer to
149 the laboratories.

150 The following elements were analysed in the water within both CWs and outside: Fe, Cu, Zn, Mn, As, Pb,
151 Cr, Ni, Cd, B, Al and Hg. The multi-elemental analyses were performed using an Agilent 7900 ICP-MS
152 in the support facilities for research at the University of Valencia (SCSIE).

153 Wide-scope screening and target quantitative analysis of pesticides were performed (Bijlsma et al. 2021).
154 Pesticide extraction from water samples was carried out by solid-phase extraction, following the
155 procedure described in Masiá et al. (2013). In brief, we used EB2 cartridges (Scharlab, Barcelona, Spain,
156 200 mg, 90 µm) preconditioned with 5 mL dichloromethane–methanol (1:1, v/v) and 10 mL deionized
157 water. A volume of 200-400 mL sample was loaded through the cartridge using a Visiprep™ SPE
158 vacuum manifold (Supelco, Bellefonte, PA, USA). The cartridges were dried for 10 min under vacuum
159 and then analytes were eluted with 10 mL dichloromethane–methanol (1:1, v/v). The sample extracts
160 were evaporated to dryness in a rotary evaporator, reconstituted with 1 mL of methanol, and filtered
161 through 0.22 µm PTFE syringe filters.

162 Pesticide identification was carried out by liquid chromatography-high resolution tandem mass
163 spectrometry (LC-HRMS/MS), using an AB SCIEX (Redwood City, CA, USA) TripleTOFTM 5600
164 system (at SCSIE, UV). Chromatographic separation was performed using an Acquity UPLC BEH C18
165 (Waters Corporation, Milford, MA, USA, 50 x 2.1 mm, 1.7 µm) column and 0.4 mL min⁻¹ mobile phase
166 of 0.1 % formic acid in water and 0.1 % formic acid in acetonitrile. HRMS acquisitions were carried out

167 using electrospray ionization in positive and negative modes, using a mass range of 100-950 m/z. Data
168 was evaluated using AB SCIEX PeakView™ software and a pesticide database of 560 compounds (see
169 Table S1, in Supplementary Material).

170 *Environmental risk assessment*

171 The environmental risk evaluation of the detected and quantified pesticides was performed based on the
172 calculation of the risk quotients (RQs). This quotient was calculated, for each pesticide, as the ratio
173 between the measured environmental concentration (MEC) and the predicted no-effect concentration
174 (PNEC), the concentration at which no toxic effects are expected in aquatic organisms (Rico et al. 2013).
175 The selection of the toxicity values in the derivation of PNECs are indicated in Table 4. The lowest PNEC
176 values were obtained from the NORMAN Ecotoxicology Database (<https://bit.ly/2Cm4zOE>). The
177 pesticides' concentrations measured in all the within-CWs (and outside) sites during the studied period
178 were averaged. Thus, an annual average for each CW and outside was considered for the RQ calculation.
179 Ecological risks were determined as insignificant or negligible risk with $RQ < 0.1$, low risk with
180 $0.1 < RQ \leq 1$, moderate risk with $1 < RQ \leq 10$, and high risk with $RQ > 10$ (García-Galán et al. 2020; Rico
181 et al. 2013).

182 *Statistical analyses*

183 We carried out the Shapiro-Wilk and the Levene tests to assess the normality of the residuals and the
184 homoscedasticity, respectively. When both conditions were verified, ANOVAs were performed.
185 Otherwise, non-parametric tests (i.e., Mann-Whitney and Kruskal-Wallis tests) were used for
186 comparisons between two, or more than two data groups, respectively. In this vein, we compared the
187 seasonal means of metal concentrations in the water of both CWs (TLI and TM). We also compared the
188 annual means of heavy metal water concentrations between TLI and TM. The annual means of the sites
189 outside the CWs were also compared: both with each other, and with the annual inside mean in each CW.
190 ANOVAs or non-parametric tests were performed to compare annual means of quantified pesticides
191 between both CWs. Statistically significant differences were considered from a probability $P < 0.05$. All
192 the analyses were performed using the PAST 3.14 software (Hammer et al. 2001;
193 ohammer@nhm.uio.no).

194

195 **Results**

196 *Heavy and other metals (metalloids)*

197 *Tancat L'Illa (TLI)*

198 Detailed concentrations of each element by site and by season are provided in Fig. S1 in the
199 Supplementary Material section. The correlations among the elements are shown in Table S2. Mean
200 Boron (B) concentrations inside the CW slightly increased from autumn-winter to late summer (although
201 the overall differences were not statistically significant). and were always higher than in the water outside
202 (Fig. 2). For the rest of the elements, no clear seasonal patterns were detected. The Chromium (Cr) mean
203 concentration was statistically lower in autumn, and Mercury (Hg) was statistically lower in autumn, late
204 spring and early summer (Fig. 2).

205 Seven out of 12 (58%) of the studied elements were reduced as water passed along the several sectors of
206 the CW (Table 1). Aluminium was the element removed with the highest mean efficiency (88%
207 reduction), followed by Zinc (57%), and Manganese and Nickel (45%). Hg was removed by 31%, and Cr
208 and Lead by 19% and 14%, respectively. However, B accumulated by 56%, Iron and Cadmium by
209 approximately 30%, and Copper by more than 100%. The case of Arsenic was the most outstanding with
210 more than 600% of mean accumulation (Table 1).

211 The reduction in Zn, Ni, Hg and Cr water concentrations caused by the CW makes their values in the
212 outlet similar to those outside the CW (approx. $2 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, $1 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, $0.1 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ and $0.1 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, respectively;
213 see Fig. S1). However, Al and Pb concentrations in the outlet remained higher than outside the CWs (0.76
214 vs $1.51 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, 0.03 vs $0.11 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, respectively). Mn remained lower in the outlet (16.7 vs $4.7 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$).
215 Among those elements which were accumulated within the CW, the concentrations of Fe, Cd and Cu
216 remained quite similar in the outlet in comparison to outside the CW (6.1 vs $6.2 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, 0.004 vs $0.005 \mu\text{g}$
217 L^{-1} , 0.4 vs $0.5 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, respectively). However, B and As concentrations outside were 1.8 and 3.3 times
218 higher than in the outlet (125 vs $224 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ and 2.3 vs $7.6 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, respectively).

219 *Tancat Mília (TM)*

220 No clear seasonal patterns were observed in the studied elements (Fig. 2). Only Ni and Cr showed a slight
221 increase from autumn to summer, but with no statistical differences. Half of the studied elements were
222 reduced as water passed through the CW (Table 1). Cu was the element which experienced the highest

223 reduction (65%), Zn and Mn showed mean reduction efficiencies of approximately 50%, Ni and Fe 36%
224 and 23%, respectively, and finally Cr only 15%. A slight accumulation was measured for Hg (8%), Cd
225 accumulated by 35%. B, Al and Pb had accumulations of more than 100%. Arsenic, as in the case of TLI,
226 accumulated by more than 500% (Table 1).

227 The reduction of Cu and Zn caused the mean concentrations in the outlet to be lower than outside the CW
228 (0.22 vs 0.47 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ and 3.5 vs 4.0 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ respectively; Fig. S2); Cr remained in similar concentrations
229 (0.14 vs 0.11 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$). However, for Ni, Fe and Mn, and despite the reduction exerted by the CW, the
230 mean concentrations in the outlet remained higher than outside (2.9 vs 1.2 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, 4.0 vs 1.8 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ and 3
231 vs 2 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, respectively). Regarding the elements accumulated within the CW, the concentrations of Cd
232 (0.005 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) and Hg (0.09 vs 0.08 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) remained quite similar in the outlet in comparison to outside
233 the CW. However, B, Pb, Al and As concentrations were 1.8, 1.9, 2.3 and 3 times higher in the outlet than
234 outside (229 vs 123 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, 0.029 vs 0.015 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, 1.8 vs 0.8 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ and 5.9 vs 2.0 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, respectively).

235 Furthermore, comparing TLI and TM, it is remarkable that the pair-wise correlation among elements
236 showed a particular pattern in each CW (Table S2).

237 *Pesticides*

238 *Tancat L'Illa (TLI)*

239 A total of 71 pesticides (26 herbicides, 26 insecticides and 19 fungicides) were detected in the water
240 samples within and outside the CW (the detailed list can be found in Table S3, Supplementary Material).
241 Out of the 71 compounds, 23 (6 fungicides, 10 herbicides and 7 insecticides) were detected only in one
242 sample (out of 24 samples analysed). A total of 57 pesticides were found in the water within the CW (21
243 herbicides, 19 insecticides and 17 fungicides) versus 38 pesticides outside (15 insecticides, 13 fungicides
244 and 10 herbicides).

245 Concerning seasonal patterns in the number of detected pesticides (Fig. 3a; see also Fig. S3; in both
246 figures, compounds that appeared only once during the entire study period are not included), the highest
247 number was found in early spring both inside and outside the CW (16 and 17, respectively), followed by
248 late summer (16 inside and 10 outside). The lowest number was observed in winter (3 inside and 4
249 outside). Specifically, a progressive decrease in the number of fungicides and insecticides was found after
250 early spring. The herbicides showed a gradual increase from early spring to late summer.

251 Regarding spatial patterns within the CW in the number of total pesticides (Fig. 3a, compounds that
252 appeared only once during the entire study period are not included), these decreased progressively as
253 water flowed through in autumn, late spring and late summer. Only in early spring did the number of
254 compounds slightly increase. By type of pesticides, the number of fungicides decreased inside the CW in
255 autumn and late spring, the number of herbicides decreased in late spring and late summer, the number of
256 insecticides increased progressively inside the CW in winter, early and late spring and late summer. In the
257 inside-outside comparison, in most seasons, the number of pesticides outside was greater than in the water
258 at the end of the system (I3).

259 The fungicides Fenpropimorph, Azoxystrobin, Carboxin, Pyrimethanil and Tricyclazole were the most
260 represented compounds (detected in 11, 10 and 9 out of the 24 samples; Table S3). Fenpropimorph could
261 not be quantified but it was detected from early spring to early summer mainly within the CW.
262 Azoxystrobin (Table 2) was detected mainly in autumn with a maximum concentration of $1 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ outside
263 the CW, and a minimum of $0.009 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ in the I2 in late summer. Tricyclazole was found within the CW
264 from late spring, and the maximum concentration was again outside the CW in autumn with $0.083 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$.
265 Carboxin was found both within and outside the CW only in the spring samplings. Pyrimethanil was
266 found in most seasons and sites (with the exception of autumn and late summer). Tebuconazole and
267 Thiabendazole were less represented, and the maximum concentration was $0.1 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ for the former and
268 $3.7 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ for the latter (Table 2).

269 The herbicides Clethodim and Hexazinone were the most represented compounds (Table S3), found in 9
270 and 6 samples (out of 24). Clethodim-imin-sulfone was detected from early spring to late summer, but its
271 spatial representation decreased with time. Hexazinone was found mainly within the CW and spatially
272 scattered. Diuron was detected on three occasions with maximum concentrations of $0.11 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ in I2
273 (Table 2).

274 The insecticides Carbofuran and Jasmolin I and the synergist Piperonyl butoxide, were the most
275 represented compounds (Table S3), each found on 4 occasions. Carbofuran showed the highest
276 concentrations in autumn in I1 and I2 (approximately $0.4 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$; Table 2). Jasmolin I was found only
277 within the final sectors of the CW in spring and late summer. Piperonyl butoxide was detected only in the
278 cold seasons (Table S3).

279

280 *Tancat Milia (TM)*

281 A total of 71 pesticides (29 herbicides, 23 insecticides and 19 fungicides) were detected within and
282 outside TM (the detailed list can be found in Table S3, Supplementary Material). Out of the 71
283 compounds, 21 (5 fungicides, 6 herbicides and 10 insecticides) were detected only in one sample (out of
284 25 samples analysed). A total of 65 pesticides (28 herbicides, 19 insecticides and 18 fungicides) were
285 found in water samples within the CW, versus 29 pesticides outside (10 herbicides, 10 insecticides and 9
286 fungicides).

287 With regard to seasonal patterns (Fig. 3b and Fig. S3), the maximum number of pesticides within the CW
288 was reached in early spring (25 compounds), with a large decline immediately after, and the minimum
289 number in autumn (4 compounds). In contrast, outside the CW, the maximum was observed in late spring
290 (12 compounds) and the minimum in winter and early summer (3 compounds). Both inside and outside
291 the CW, the number of fungicides experienced a progressive increase until spring, followed by a decrease
292 later on. Only inside the CW did the herbicides and insecticides increase their presence from autumn to
293 early spring.

294 Regarding spatial patterns (Fig. 3b), a decrease in the total number of pesticides was observed as the
295 water flowed through the CW in winter, early spring and early and late summer. With regard to the types
296 of pesticides, the number of fungicides decreased in late spring and early and late summer; the number of
297 herbicides decreased in winter, early spring and early summer, and the number of insecticides decreased
298 only in late summer. In the inside-outside comparison, only in half of the seasons was the water (M3)
299 returned outside with a lower number of pesticides than the number found in the surroundings.

300 The fungicides Azoxystrobin, Pyrimethanil, Fenpropimorph, Carboxin, and Tebuconazole were the most
301 represented compounds (detected in 15, 12, 11, 9 and 8 out of the 25 samples). Azoxystrobin was found
302 in all seasons and sites, with the exception of early summer (Table 2; Table S3). The maximum
303 concentration was $0.53 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ outside the CW and the minimum $0.018 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ in M2 in late summer
304 (Table 2). Pyrimethanil was present from winter, with higher concentrations in M1 (see Table S3).
305 Fenpropimorph was detected from early spring, both within and outside the CW, and its relative
306 concentration decreased later on. Carboxin was detected only during the spring in all sites. Tebuconazole
307 was detected from early spring until early summer, with maximum concentrations of $0.047 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ in M3
308 in late spring. Tricyclazole was found only within the CW, mainly at the end of the system (M3), with

309 maximum concentrations of 0.013 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$. Thiabendazole was found only in three samples in summer,
310 with maximum concentrations of 1.7 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ (Table 2). None of the quantified fungicides showed
311 significant differences in the annual means between both CWs (Table S4).

312 The herbicides Clethodim, Sebuthylazine, Simazine, Terbutylazine, Hexazinone and Diuron were the
313 most represented compounds (Table S3), found in 8, 7, 6 and 5 samples (out of 25). Clethodim-imin-
314 sulfone was detected from early spring to late summer mainly inside the CW and with higher relative
315 concentrations than in TLI (see Table S3). Sebuthylazine-desethyl, Simazine and Terbutylazine-desethyl
316 were found outside the CW from autumn, but with higher relative concentrations within the CW in late
317 summer. Hexazinone was found only within the CW with higher relative concentration in early spring.
318 Diuron was also detected only inside the CW, mainly in sector B, with a maximum concentration of 0.07
319 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ in I2 (Table 2). As occurred with fungicides, the mean annual concentration of the quantified
320 Diuron was not significantly different between TLI and TM (Table S4).

321 The insecticides Carbofuran Jasmolin I, and Tebufenozide, and Piperonyl butoxide were the most
322 represented compounds (Table S3), each found on (7) 8 occasions. Carbofuran was found exclusively
323 within the CW mainly in late summer; the highest concentrations were measured in autumn in M2 and
324 M3 (approximately 0.2 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$; Table 2). Jasmolin I was found only in early spring within all sectors of
325 the CW as well as outside, but its relative concentration decreased as water passed along the CW.
326 Piperonyl butoxide was detected mainly in early summer, but the highest relative concentration was found
327 in autumn outside the CW (Table S3). Tebufenozide was represented from late spring, and the higher
328 relative concentrations at M1 were substantially reduced in M2 and M3. Dimethoate and Imidacloprid
329 were detected sporadically (1 occasion each) with concentrations of 0.7 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ and 0.08 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$,
330 respectively (Table 2). Again, there were no significant differences in the mean annual concentrations of
331 insecticides between both CWs (Table S4).

332 *Risk assessment of the quantified pesticides*

333 Regarding the environmental risk assessment for freshwater (Table 4), the calculated RQs show that most
334 pesticides pose negligible or low risk both within and outside the CWs. The fungicide Thiabendazole and
335 the insecticide Imidacloprid are the only ones posing a moderate risk for both CWs in the first case, and
336 only for TM, in the second.

337

338 Discussion

339 *Heavy metals and other trace elements*

340 Tertiary treatment is of importance when treated wastewater is discharged into sensitive ecosystems such
341 as wetlands, rivers, lakes or used in groundwater regeneration or agriculture. Tertiary treatment in
342 wastewater treatment plants may use chemical reagents (coagulants, flocculants) to increase nutrient
343 removal efficiencies (Iborra-Clar et al. 2011). TLI may have received wastewater enriched in Al, Zn, Ni,
344 Hg, Pb and Cr, since the concentrations of these elements are much higher in the first sector (which
345 receives the wastewater directly without passing through any sub-superficial-flow sector) of the CW than
346 in the receptor waterbody (*Estany de la Plana*). *Sueca* sewage water treatment plant uses aluminium
347 polychloride as a coagulant in the tertiary treatment (the most widely used coagulant type at present;
348 Rahmadyanti et al. 2021), as well as a cationic polyelectrolyte in previous treatments. However, the water
349 concentrations of Al, and the rest of the elements, are efficiently reduced as water flows through the
350 different sectors of the CW. Several studies have reported the reduction of heavy metals through
351 microbial and plant biomass in CWs, by means of two main mechanisms: the active one being energy-
352 dependent bioaccumulation, and the passive one energy-independent biosorption (by the adsorption
353 mechanism) (Malyan et al. 2021; Yu et al. 2021). For example, Bianchi et al. (2021) reported biosorption
354 through macrophyte species, such as *Phragmites australis* (the role of reed biomass as a biosorbent
355 material yields the removal of Zn by 73%, under optimum dose and experimental conditions). Previously,
356 Southichak et al. (2006) also reported the biosorption of Ni, Pb and Zn through reed biomass. The above-
357 cited mechanisms (facilitated by the presence of emergent vegetation, mainly *Typha* spp., but also some
358 *Phragmites* spp., and the microbial activity in the water and sediment; Wang et al. 2022) explain the
359 reduction of these metals in TLI. It is worth pointing out that this water removal effect, particularly for
360 Al, is totally produced within the first *B* sector, since water from last *B* sector and *C* sector already have
361 concentrations equal to the surrounding waters. The wide water surface and slow flow of the aerobic zone
362 of wetlands enhances the bacterial metal oxidation and the following hydroxylation, which causes the
363 precipitation of Fe, Mn and Al hydroxides (Luko-Sulato et al. 2021). Moreover, the precipitated
364 oxyhydroxides of Fe and Mn can absorb other heavy metals, such as Pb, Ni and Cr (Matagi et al. 1998).
365 Mn is also oxidized by the microorganisms from the bivalent Mn (II) to tetravalent Mn (IV) and then Mn
366 (IV) is precipitated as manganese oxide (Malyan et al. 2021). Moreover, in wetlands, the complexation of
367 metals can be facilitated by the presence of organic molecules (e.g., tannic, fulvic, and humic acids)

368 which are nucleophile or mostly multidentate ligands that interact with heavy metals, influencing their
369 solubility and mobility (Weng et al. 2002). The presence of such organic molecules is evident in TLI,
370 particularly in I2 (the last *B* sector) whose water has an evident reddish colour.

371 For the other elements, TLI functions the opposite way; B, Fe, Cd, Cu and As are accumulated in the CW
372 waters. Boron is a metalloid which is widely used in several industrial activities, such as the production of
373 cleaning products, glass and agrochemicals. Due to its high solubility, it is easily found in anthropic
374 waters (Türker et al. 2014). Atmospheric precipitation and aerosols are another input of B to aquatic
375 systems, along with marine salts. Thus, in water bodies close to the sea, as is the case of the TLI,
376 relatively high concentrations are expected. However, the use of perborate products increases B
377 concentrations in domestic wastewater, and little or no B is removed during conventional wastewater
378 treatment processes (Türker et al. 2014). The results of domestic wastewater discharge can contribute to
379 the elevated B concentration inside the CW compared to the site outside (Fig. 2). In the *Albufera* lagoon,
380 the B concentrations are also lower ($130 \pm 13 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ as annual mean for 2020-2021; CHJ, 2022). The
381 chemistry of B differs from that of other trace elements, and the overall B removal process in CWs is very
382 complex, making the identification of specific removal pathways more difficult (Türker et al. 2014).
383 Several experiments in microcosms and mesocosms have documented B removal, but the rates of removal
384 in full-scale CWs is low (see references in the review of Türker et al. 2014). Several environmental
385 factors such as pH, temperature, B speciation and seasonal effects can affect the B concentration in CWs
386 water. The highest accumulation within TLI is observed in early and late summer, and this can be
387 explained because both the solubility rates of B compounds and the dissociation of boric acid increase as
388 temperature increases (Tu et al. 2010). Copper compounds are commonly used in agriculture to treat plant
389 pests or for water treatment (Zandi et al. 2020). The different use in agriculture depending on the season
390 would explain the different concentrations of Cu outside the TLI (maximum of $1 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ in early summer
391 and undetectable values in late summer). The mean Cu accumulation rates in TLI are mainly due to the
392 warm period data; the rest of the year no accumulation happens, but nor was a reduction observed, as has
393 been described for other CWs treating domestic wastewater (Arroyo et al. 2010). Cd can proceed from the
394 manufacture and application of phosphate fertilizers. The performance of TLI on Cd, although yielding an
395 annual mean accumulation as water passed along the CW, when the system received the highest
396 concentrations (as high as $0.018 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ in winter time), can reduce it to almost undetectable values at the
397 outlet. Arsenic has a predominantly geogenic or mining-derived origin in Iberian Peninsula paddy field

398 soils (Signes-Pastor et al. 2016) and deserves special attention due to its accumulation in TLI, since it has
399 been described how the stable complexation of As, in association with dissolved organic matter and Fe
400 and solid phase humic substances (Mandal et al. 2019), act as the main sinks of As in water-saturated
401 sediment, as in the case of these CWs. But, at the same time, the increase in As in outlet concentrations
402 has been amply reported in the literature for different types of CWs (Arroyo et al. 2010 and references
403 therein). Arsenic has the highest concentrations in sector C in TLI, a pond-like waterbody with emergent
404 vegetation only on the shores and with moderate coverage of submerged vegetation only during the
405 warmer periods. It seems that the highest As concentrations in the pond happen during the moments of
406 greater coverage of submerged plants (mainly *Myriophyllum spicatum* and also *Najas marina* which
407 outcompete *M. spicatum* in the late summer). One could expect that the submerged plants could have
408 changed the redox potential of the sediment to more oxidized conditions and produced the sink of As.
409 However, it seems that the conditions developed in sector C by submerged vegetation were not able to
410 maintain stable oxidised conditions to guarantee As removal by combination with oxides (Pedescoll et al.
411 2015). On the other hand, the higher presence of humic acids in the B sectors in comparison to sector C
412 could be responsible for the lower As concentrations, due to the complexation capacity on metalloids,
413 such as As, of these substances (Mandal et al. 2019). More attention should be paid to humic substance
414 composition in CWs, particularly facing climate change since, as Lipczynska-Kochany (2018) pointed
415 out, this has a clear induced impact on humic compounds and their interactions with soil and water
416 pollutants such as metals. Regarding Hg, one of the most toxic heavy metals, particularly in its
417 methylated form (Regnell and Watras 2019), TLI is capable of “neutralizing” the higher concentrations
418 probably arriving with the wastewater in winter and early spring.

419 The performance of TM is very similar to that of TLI for several elements (very similar removal for Zn,
420 Mn, Ni and Cr; similar accumulation for Cd, B and As) and the mechanisms involved in both CWs must
421 be the same since the design of the two CWs is similar. Regarding Cd, this CW, again, is capable of
422 reducing the highest concentrations in autumn in the inlet to less than a half in the outlet. However, a
423 relevant difference is the concentrations of Al between the two CWs, and the explanation is because, in
424 the case of TM, aluminium polychloride is not used as a coagulant in the tertiary treatment in the *Albufera*
425 *Sur* sewage water treatment plant. Instead, ferric chloride is used, and this must be the reason why Fe has
426 a statistically higher concentration inside the CW rather than outside (Fig. 4). A source of Pb in the area
427 can be related to the use of lead ammunition, since the Natural Park had been used for hunting activities

428 practiced for decades until the implementation of *Real Decreto* 581/2001 (which was not totally effective
429 until 2003), which banned the use of Pb ammunition for hunting in internationally relevant wetlands
430 (Valverde et al. 2019). Lead shot pellets remained in the sediments for years and the construction of the
431 CWs, using machinery, could have moved deeper sediments corresponding to the hunting period
432 upwards. This would explain why the annual Pb means are significantly higher within the CW compared
433 to outside both CWs (Fig. 4). The statistically higher Ni mean concentrations within TM in comparison to
434 TLI and outside (and in the *Albufera* lagoon: $<1.2 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$; CHJ, 2022) are related to the input water, since
435 in five out of the six occasions the Ni concentration was clearly higher in M1 (see Fig. S4). On the other
436 hand, one important difference between both CWs is the presence of a sub-superficial-water flow sector
437 (A) only in TM. However, it seems its existence is not relevant for the concentrations of most of the
438 elements, since there were no statistically significant differences between the mean annual concentrations
439 when I1 and M1 were compared. Only B, Al and Pb show a 30%, 82 % and 84%, respectively, lower
440 values in TM than in TLI (Fig. S4). Aluminum differences have been discussed above.

441 *Metal concentrations to be discharged from both CWs in comparison to legal restrictions*

442 TLI manages to reduce (Mn) or to maintain at the same level the concentration of most of the studied
443 elements (Zn, Ni, Hg, Cr, Fe Cd, Cu) as outside (67%). Only Al, Pb, B and As are at higher
444 concentrations. TM also reduces Zn and Cu, and maintains the concentration of Cr, Cd and Hg (which
445 represents 42%). Al, Pb, B and As remain at higher concentrations, as occurs in TLI, but also Ni, Fe and
446 Mn are at higher concentrations. The European Union establishes the environmental quality standards for
447 priority substances in continental waters, registered for Spain in *Real Decreto* 817/2015 (BOE 219, 12-
448 09-2015). The annual means of Pb concentrations in the outlets of TLI and TM (0.11 ± 0.06 –standard
449 deviation– and $0.03 \pm 0.02 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, respectively) are far lower than the EU quality standards ($7.2 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$).
450 These means for B in the outlets of TLI ($224 \pm 78 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) and TM ($229 \pm 42 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) are also below the limit
451 recommended by the World Health Organization ($500 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$). For Al ($1.5 \pm 0.5 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ and $1.8 \pm 1.5 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$
452 for TLI and TM, respectively), which is not listed in the standards cited above, the limit for drinking
453 water is $200 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$. Even for As ($7.6 \pm 3.7 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ and $5.9 \pm 4.4 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$), which is the element with a higher
454 concentration in the outlet in comparison to outside the CWs; both CW mean concentrations are far below
455 the quality standards for priority substances in continental waters ($50 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) or other superficial waters
456 ($25 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$). Ni concentrations in TM ($2.9 \pm 1.1 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) are one order of magnitude lower than the EU
457 standards ($20 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$). Fe and Mn are not listed in the EU standards cited above, but the limit for drinking

458 water is established at 200-300 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ and 50 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ respectively, and in the TM outlet both mean
459 concentrations ($4\pm 2 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ and $3\pm 3 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, respectively) are clearly below these thresholds.

460 For the rest of the elements, mean concentrations in both CW outlets are also below the limits of the
461 quality standards of the EU for priority substances in continental waters (hexavalent Cr=5 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, Cr=50
462 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$; Cu=5-120 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ and Zn=30-500 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ depending on the water hardness; Cd<0.08 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ and
463 $\leq 0.45 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ as admissible maximum). Hg is the only element whose mean concentrations in both outlets
464 ($0.10\pm 0.06 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ and $0.09\pm 0.05 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ for TLI and TM, respectively) are above the limit for priority
465 substances ($0.05 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$), and even slightly higher than the admissible maximum concentration ($0.07 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$). Overall, the waters surrounding the CWs also have annual mean concentrations slightly above these
466 limits (0.09 and $0.08 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ for sites outside TLI and TM, respectively), since these areas receive waters
467 discharged from the rice fields with agrochemicals and pesticide residues derived from the rice farming
468 activity, as occurs in other areas of the Spanish Mediterranean coast (Salvadó et al. 2006). In the *Albufera*
469 lagoon no Hg values above $0.02 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ were measured in our study period (CHJ, 2022). However, in
470 previous years, one-time values of 0.08 - $0.09 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ were recorded in October 2018 and January 2019.

472 *Pesticides*

473 The presence of pesticides in both CWs is related to the fact that they are immersed in an agrolandscape
474 mainly based in the cultivation of rice, but also other crops (citrus, vegetables, potatoes, etc.; Gamón et al.
475 2003; Köck et al. 2010; Hedge et al. 2014; Rico et al. 2018; Calvo et al. 2021). Several compounds are
476 used as treatments to control pests annually by means of aerial and terrestrial methods in the 14.000 ha
477 covered by rice fields within the Natural Park. Although both CWS showed the same elevated number of
478 pesticides in their water, the composition was not exactly equal. Moreover, 32% (TLI area) and 29% (TM
479 area) of the compounds were detected only in a single sample, and 19% (TLI) and 13% (TM) in only two
480 samples (Table 3). The number of pesticides which are present in more than 25% of samples is low, and
481 of the same order as those compounds found in more than 40% of samples (3%). TM is clearly more
482 affected by pesticides than TLI, not only regarding the number of pesticides (35 versus 24 exclusive
483 compounds in TM and TLI, respectively) temporally but also spatially (see Table S3). The application of
484 pesticides in the Natural Park is somehow different depending on the particular area. Although there are
485 some general rules/legislation (Generalitat Valenciana 2008; 2020), each area is treated slightly
486 differently. The rice cultivation treatments start with the use of herbicides against the weeds, and only

487 when rice plants are growing are the fungicides used to avoid or reduce the presence of plagues
488 responsible for rice diseases (Calvo et al. 2021). In our case, the number of herbicides detected in early
489 spring was one of the highest, particularly for TM. The herbicides Clethodim-imin-sulfone (a metabolite
490 of Clethodim) and Hexazinone were found within both CWs, but mainly in TM. Clethodim is a
491 graminicide applied postemergence to control annual grasses (Jordan, 2011) and it is usually applied
492 combined with other graminicides (Jordan et al. 2003). Diuron, found also within both CWs (more
493 sporadically in TLI), classified as priority substances in Annex X Directive, 2000/60/EEC, did not surpass
494 the annual means ($0.2 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) or the maximum concentrations ($1.8 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) established in Annex II of
495 Directive, 2013/39/EU for continental surface waters (or Real Decreto 817/2015). The herbicide
496 Bentazone, one of the two most abundant pesticides in the *Albufera de València* Natural Park aquatic
497 systems in 2016 (Calvo et al. 2021), although detected in the surroundings of TM in March 2021, it was
498 not found within TM or TLI. The application of this herbicide by tractor in the rice fields prevented its
499 presence within both CWs. The three herbicides Simazine, Terbutylazine-desethyl and Terbutryn were
500 found exclusively in TM and their pattern of appearance is very similar (mainly in the last sampling: late
501 summer). Simazine is also referred in Annex II of Directive, 2013/39/EU for continental surface waters
502 (or Real Decreto 817/2015), but we cannot say if it surpasses, or not, the annual means ($1 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) or the
503 maximum concentrations ($4 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) since we were not able to quantify it, but probably not, since
504 Simazine has been also detected in *Albufera de València* lagoon waters (southern part) with mean
505 concentrations for 2020-2021 of $0.015 \pm 0.007 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ (CHJ, 2022). The use of Terbutryn was forbidden
506 by Regulation (EC) 2076/2002; we could not quantify it, but in the south part of the *Albufera* lagoon it is
507 $< 0.01 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ (CHJ, 2022). Terbutylazine-desethyl is a residue of Terbutylazine, which remains
508 approved. These compounds are non-specific herbicides which have been widely used in the production
509 of corn, wheat and potatoes, among others (Chhokar and Sharma 2008; Stipičević et al. 2015; Hormenoo
510 et al. 2021).

511 Fungicides were the most represented pesticides, and 12 were common to both CWs (Table 3).
512 Azoxystrobin and Difenoconazole are applied together under the brand name of Amistar Top (Syngenta,
513 Basilea, Switzerland) and are supplied in two runs, at the end of July and at the end of August, on the rice
514 fields by helicopter (*Generalitat Valenciana*, 2021); the former was detected both outside and within the
515 CWs (42 % and 60% of samples in TLI and TM, respectively), and the highest concentrations were found
516 in late September 2020 and early September 2021. Its presence within the CWs is evidently related to the

517 application method, since the CWs are completely surrounded by rice fields. However, Difenconazole
518 was detected sporadically, mainly outside the CWs and with a higher presence at the end of September
519 2020. This compound degrades more easily and rapidly than Azoxystrobin (Meenakshi et al. 2007). The
520 fungicide Tricyclazole, found within both CWs, is a post-emergence fungicide which was usually sprayed
521 from mid-July until the rice harvest; however, this active substance was not approved by Commission
522 Implementing Regulation (EU) 2016/1826 and, thus, all existing authorisations for plant protection
523 products containing Tricyclazole were revoked. Nevertheless, the use of this chemical has been allowed
524 in some years as a terrestrial and aerial treatment by the Agricultural Ministry of Spain with exceptional
525 authorizations (it could be sprayed twice in one treatment after an interval of 15–20 days). In 2016, Calvo
526 et al. (2021) found that Tricyclazole was dominant (88–100 %) from the beginning of rice cultivation in
527 the four aquatic systems analysed (the *Albufera* lagoon, rice fields, irrigation and outlet channels), with
528 peak values in September 2016 (3.3 to 6.6 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ in channels and rice fields and 5.9 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ in the *Albufera*
529 lagoon). Currently, our values are much lower (maximum of 0.08 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ at the end of September 2020).
530 Tricyclazole has been described by its high solubility, its persistence in the water and the lack of stability
531 to photolysis in the water. However, based on results of an experimental field study, Tsochatzis et al.
532 (2013) reported that Tricyclazole is not really persistent in rice field water, probably due to degradation or
533 volatilization processes and its adsorption by the field sediments. Our results were able to corroborate this
534 observation since its concentrations in the water were low. It also could indicate that this fungicide is
535 currently applied (although it does not appear in the list of permitted substances; MAPA, 2021) in lower
536 doses. We have no information about how and when this fungicide was applied in 2020-2021. Two more
537 fungicides were found in both CWs, Tebuconazole and Thiabendazole. Tebuconazole has been one of the
538 most common and abundantly found in the *Albufera de València* Natural Park in other studies (Calvo et
539 al. 2021), also currently in the southern part of *Albufera* lagoon at concentrations $< 0.01 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ (CHJ,
540 2022). Tebuconazole is used post-harvest not only in rice but also in citrus crops. This agrochemical is
541 used at the beginning of July and could be used until August or September depending on the strength of
542 the pyricularia (*Magnaporthe oryzae*) disease in the year of the cultivation. It has low or moderate
543 solubility and is bio-accumulative; it has been reported how its persistence in water field samples does not
544 last more than 4–5 days (Fu et al. 2016). This is why the concentrations found in our study are not high
545 (maximum of 0.1 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$). Thiabendazole is not used for rice cultivation, but it is used in other crops such
546 as citrus (oranges and tangerines) and potatoes which are also cultivated within the area of the Natural

547 Park. Calvo et al. (2021) found this compound in concentrations lower than $0.1 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, but we detected it
548 in higher concentrations, occasionally at $3.7 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$. The fungicide Carbendazim, which was prohibited
549 before 2016, was detected just in one sample within TLI. Merel et al. (2018) reported that textiles and
550 papers commonly found in households could be a source of Carbendazim in domestic wastewater. Thus,
551 the effluents of the wastewater treatment plants might be a source of this compound. Some other
552 fungicides which were applied in the past in the area, such as Propiconazole, and that are currently
553 forbidden, were not detected.

554 The insecticides Carbofuran and Jasmolin I, and the synergist Piperonyl butoxide, were common in both
555 CWs, and they were the most represented; along with Tebufenozide in TM. Carbofuran, Jasmolin I, and
556 Tebufenozide were not detected by Calvo et al. (2021) in 2016. Carbofuran is a systemic granular
557 insecticide frequently used to combat insects in rice cultivation (Das et al. 2003). In Spain it was excluded
558 from the list of permitted phytosanitary products (MAPA, 2020) following ONU guidelines where this
559 compound is included in the Consolidated List of Prohibited or Restricted Products. Jasmolin I is an
560 insecticide from the group of pyrethrines mainly affecting the nervous system of diverse insects.
561 Furthermore, Piperonyl butoxide is commonly used as an insecticide synergist which enhances the active
562 properties of pyrethrines (Schleier III et al. 2008). This fact could explain the joint presence of these
563 compounds in both CWs. Tebufenozide is a synthetic insect growth regulator which exhibits insecticidal
564 activity by inducing premature and incomplete moulting of larvae of various lepidopteran insect pests
565 (Gómez de Barreda Ferraz et al. 2004). These authors assessed the effect of this insecticide on
566 phytoplanktonic species from the *Albufera de València* Natural Park. The neonicotinoid insecticides
567 Acetamiprid and Imidacloprid are usually applied in the area at the beginning of July by tractor. Both
568 insecticides were the most detected ones in the July water samples in the study by Calvo et al. (2021). The
569 dissipation of neonicotinoids seems to be largely dominated by photolysis and temperature (Rico et al.
570 2018). Both are soluble in water and have a low capability of bioaccumulation; Acetamiprid persist in the
571 water less than a week. All this, together with the type of application, are the reasons why they were not
572 detected in our samples (only Imidacloprid was found within TM in M1 in early summer with $<0.1 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$).
573 ¹⁾.

574 One of our aims was to assess how pesticide composition can be modified as water provided by the
575 wastewater treatment plants passes along the CWs. We have seen that the most ubiquitous pesticides
576 (e.g., Azoxystrobin and Difenoconazole) arrive by aerial dispersal. But the water course throughout the

577 different sectors of the CWs causes the decrease in the prevalence of most pesticides. Several processes
578 occurring within the CWs, such as adsorption, hydrolysis, microbial degradation, sedimentation,
579 photolysis and plant uptake play an important role in said removal of pesticides in CWs (Vymazal and
580 Březinová 2015; Malyan et al. 2021). Moreover, the concentrations of pesticides that have been
581 quantitatively analyzed (Table 2) are far below the toxic concentrations for aquatic organisms that have
582 been reported in several studies. For fungicides, Rodrigues et al. (2013) carried out a review on
583 Azoxystrobin in aquatic systems and, in the wide variety of organisms studied the toxicity of this
584 compound was above $2 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, with some organisms being able to tolerate concentrations several orders
585 of magnitude higher. Regarding Metalaxyl, studies with *Daphnia magna* (Chen and Liu, 2008) and
586 cyanobacteria (Hamed et al. 2020) showed a lethal concentration 50 (LC₅₀) of more than 50 mg L^{-1} and
587 25 mg L^{-1} , respectively. It has been reported, in laboratory studies, that Tebuconazole applied in
588 concentrations from $500 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ has negative effects on microbial communities (Zubrod et al. 2011).
589 Martín-de-Lucía et al. (2019) demonstrated in a microcosm experiment that Thiabendazole had toxic
590 effects on *D. magna* at a concentration in the water from 9 mg L^{-1} . For Tricyclazole, Rossaro and Cortesi
591 (2013) reported an LC₅₀ from 20 mg L^{-1} for different aquatic species from microfauna to fish (e.g.,
592 *Cyprinus carpio*). As for herbicides, for Diuron, an LC₅₀ has been reported ranging from 4.3 to 42.0 mg
593 L^{-1} in fish, and from 1.0 to 2.5 mg L^{-1} in aquatic invertebrates (Giacomazzi and Cochet 2004). Regarding
594 insecticides, Gunasekara et al. (2008) analyzed different aquatic species, both invertebrates and
595 vertebrates, at different stages (larvae, juveniles and adults), establishing the toxicity of Carbaryl in a
596 range between $3.6 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ and 34.7 mg L^{-1} , depending on the species. With respect to Carbofuran,
597 Dobšíková (2003) compared and analyzed the toxicity of this compound in different aquatic and
598 terrestrial species, establishing a range of 0.04- 13.08 mg L^{-1} as the LC₅₀. For Dimethoate, several studies
599 have analyzed its toxicity in aquatic organisms such as fish (toxic effects at concentrations above 1.84 mg
600 L^{-1} ; Singh et al. 2009) or rotifers (toxic effects at concentrations above 0.18 mg L^{-1} ; Guo et al. 2012).
601 Tišler et al. (2009), in an experimental setup, showed that Imidacloprid was not as toxic to some aquatic
602 organisms as other environmental pollutants, mainly affecting *D. magna* individuals at concentrations
603 above 1.3 mg L^{-1} . When the environmental risk of quantified pesticides was assessed (RQ for freshwater),
604 most compounds showed negligible to low risks (Table 4). The higher environmental risk obtained for
605 Imidacloprid in TM could be attributed to their very low PNEC value as it was concluded also by García-
606 Galán et al. (2020). Nevertheless, more in-depth study must be undertaken in this vein, with a

607 quantification of more pesticides that could be present throughout the year and in more sites both within
608 and outside the CWs, and with a better assessment of PNECs, due to the large disparity of reported values
609 for the freshwater aquatic environment (see Table 4).

610 **Final remarks and conclusions**

611 Overall, Zn, Mn, Ni, and Cr water concentrations were reduced, whereas Cd, B, and As water content
612 increased as water passed along both CWs. TLI is capable of dampening the above-legal-limit
613 concentrations of Hg supplied by wastewater at certain times, and reducing them to levels closer to the
614 European Union's legal limits for environmental quality. Although both CWs vary with regard to metal
615 removal, no risks to human health or the environment have been detected due to the low metal
616 concentrations in the outlets. However, the use of synthetic coagulants is disadvantageous due to the
617 residual aluminium content they produce, since although the CWs are capable of removing them from the
618 water they can accumulate in the sediments and/or the biota and can be deleterious in the medium/long-
619 term. Therefore, natural organic coagulants should be seen as an attractive alternative to chemicals
620 because of their abundant availability, low cost, non-toxicity, and multifunctionality (Tukki et al. 2016;
621 Rahmadyanti et al. 2021). The way the pesticides are applied in the rice fields and surrounding crops of
622 the CWs (tractor, bag spraying, helicopter) plays a determining role in their presence in the CWs waters.
623 With the wide-scope screening methodology applied in this study we have seen that TM is much more
624 affected by pesticides than TLI. However, the mechanisms facilitated by the spatial structure of the CWs,
625 (e.g. plant uptake by the continuous presence of emergent and submerged -occasionally- macrophytes,
626 adsorption, microbial degradation, sedimentation, hydrolysis, photolysis, etc.) must play an important role
627 in pesticide removal in the CWs. Now, the next step is to quantify by target quantitative analyses the
628 presence of the remaining most frequently used pesticides to unravel whether or not they are above the
629 legal limits and to calculate refined risk assessments. Moreover, their presence in the sediment of the
630 CWs and the biota (Braschi et al. 2002) needs further analyses in future campaigns, as well as the
631 participation of microorganisms in key processes of pollutant degradation (Wang et al. 2022).

632 Finally, we want to stress the crucial environmental services that both CWs provide to this particular
633 agrolandscape immersed in a protected area of international importance for biodiversity, in terms of
634 reducing the environmental impacts of treated domestic wastewater, pesticide application in the
635 surroundings and improving water quality and safety.

636 **Statements and Declarations**

637 **Author contribution:**

638 María A. Rodrigo: Conceptualization, Resources, Writing – original Draft, Writing - Review and Editing;

639 Eric Puche: Formal analysis, Visualization, Writing - Review and Editing; Nuria Carabal: Formal

640 analysis, Visualization, Writing - Original Draft; Sergio Armenta and Francesc A. Esteve-Turrillas:

641 Resources, Writing - Review and Editing; Javier Jiménez: Conceptualization, Funding acquisition;

642 Fernando Juan: Funding acquisition.

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- 933

934 **Table 1** Concentration removal efficiency based on differences in concentration between I1/I3 (or
 935 M1/M3) (in percentage, and expressed with a negative symbol) for several elements in both studied CWs.
 936 Accumulation percentage for other elements. Data are means of six samplings \pm standard deviation, and
 937 are ordered by reduction in removal and increase in accumulation. For some elements, removal was
 938 observed in one CW and accumulation for the other CW, this is why some cells are empty and the
 939 element appears in both parts of the table

		Efficiencies (%)								
		Removal								
		Al	Cu	Zn	Mn	Ni	Hg	Fe	Cr	Pb
TLI		-88 \pm 3		-57 \pm 10	-45 \pm 42	-46 \pm 6	-31 \pm 12		-19 \pm 10	-14 \pm 26
TM			-65 \pm 13	-53 \pm 12	-49 \pm 22	-36 \pm 8		-23 \pm 17	-15 \pm 12	
		Accumulation								
		Hg	Fe	Cd	B	Al	Cu	Pb	As	
TLI			29 \pm 39	35 \pm 29	56 \pm 24		118 \pm 67		644 \pm 134	
TM		8 \pm 9		35 \pm 46	123 \pm 12	192 \pm 214		153 \pm 151	519 \pm 235	

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941

942 **Table 2** Concentration (all in $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) of some pesticides detected within both CWs and outside in the
 943 different seasons (Aut: autumn 2020; Wi: winter 2021; ES_p: early spring 2021; LS_p: late spring 2021;
 944 LS_u: late summer). M0*: an extra water sample taken before the subsurface section in TM CW only in
 945 late summer (“nd” indicates there is no data)

Family	Compounds	Season	Sites in TL				Sites in TM				
			Out	I1	I2	I3	Out	M0*	M1	M2	M3
			Concentration ($\mu\text{g/l}$)				Concentration ($\mu\text{g/l}$)				
Fungicides											
<i>Methoxyacrylates (Strobilutins)</i>	Azoxystrobin	Aut	1.027	0.445	0.549	0.089	0.530	nd		0.117	0.103
		ES _p	0.033	0.041	0.022		0.105	nd	0.103	0.140	0.095
		LS _p					0.025	nd	0.039	0.014	
		ES _u	0.079					nd			
		LS _u	0.471		0.009		0.349	0.035	0.036	0.018	0.034
<i>Anilide</i>	Metaxyl	ES _p		0.039			nd				
<i>Conazole</i>	Tebuconazole	Aut		0.105				nd			0.078
		Wi		0.024				nd			
		ES _p		0.042		0.025	0.006	nd			0.018
		LS _p	0.010				0.009	nd	0.047		0.025
		ES _u						nd	0.045	0.009	
LS _u	0.032										
<i>Benzimidazole</i>	Thiabendazole	ES _p		0.619				nd			
		LS _p	0.523	3.758				nd			
		ES _u						nd	1.674		
		LS _u					1.463	1.333			
<i>Benzothiazole</i>	Tricyclazole	Aut	0.083					nd			
		Wi	0.010					nd			0.006
		ES _p						nd			0.009
		LS _p	0.010	0.018		0.012		nd		0.013	0.010
		ES _u	0.025		0.013	0.017		nd	0.008		0.013
		LS _u				0.013					
Herbicides											
<i>Phenylurea</i>	Diuron ¹	Aut			0.110			nd			
		ES _p						nd	0.008		
		LS _p						nd	0.012	0.021	
		ES _u				0.010		nd	0.066		
		LS _u		0.005						0.003	
Insecticides											
<i>Carbamate</i>	Carbaryl	LS _u					0.225				
<i>Carbamate</i>	Carbofuran	Aut		0.447	0.353			nd		0.231	0.244
		ES _u						nd	0.166		
		LS _u	0.060			0.065	0.060	0.077	0.036	0.047	
<i>Organophosphate</i>	Dimethoate	ES _u						nd	0.684		
<i>Neonicotinoid</i>	Imidacloprid ²	ES _u						nd	0.083		

946

947 ¹: Compound included in the List of Priority substances in the field of water policy (Directive
 948 2013/39/EU). The annual mean in inland surface waters listed Real Decreto 817/2015 for diuron is 0.2 μg
 949 L^{-1} and the maximum allowable concentration is 1.8 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$.

950 ²: Compound included in the Watch List (Commission implementing decision (EU) 2018/840).

951 **Table 3** Number of pesticides separated by type present exclusively outside the CWs, exclusively within
 952 the CWs, in common in the different areas. The number of compounds that appear only in one or two
 953 samples, or between 25%-40% of samples or in more than 40% of samples is also indicated (total samples
 954 for TLI: 24; for TM: 25). The percentage is referred to 71 pesticide compounds found in each CW area

Pesticide	Out			Within CW			In common Out-Within		Only 1 sample (4%)		Only 2 sample (8%)		> 25%, but <40% samples		> than 40% samples	
	excl. TLI	excl. TM	In common	excl. TLI	excl. TM	In common	TLI	TM	TLI area	TM area	TLI area	TM area	TLI area	TM area	TLI area	TM area
Herbicides	7	7	3	10	16	11	6	8	6	5	5	1	1	1	0	0
Fungicides	4	2	7	6	7	11	10	8	10	6	4	7	2	3	2	2
Insecticides	11	5	4	8	12	10	8	5	7	10	5	1	0	1	0	0
Total (number)	22	14	14	24	35	32	24	21	23	21	14	9	3	5	2	2
Total (%)									32	30	20	13	4	7	3	3

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957

Table 4 Environmental risk of pesticides detected and quantified in Tancat l'Illa (TLI), Tancat de Mília (TM) and outside the CWs (Out) as risk quotient (RQ) calculated as the proportion between the measured environmental concentration (MEC) and the predicted no-effect concentration (PNEC) for each pesticide. The MEC values were calculated as an annual average for each CW (and outside). The lowest PNECs for freshwater (*PNEC_{lowest}*, in italics) were obtained from the NORMAN Ecotoxicology Database (<https://bit.ly/2Cm4zOE>). The reference for the PNEC value used for QR calculation for each pesticide is provided. Negligible risk (<0.1); Low risk (0.1-1); Moderate risk (1-10); High risk (>10) (García-Galán et al. 2020).

Pesticides	TLI			TM		Out		*Reference
	<i>PNEC_{lowest}</i> -PNEC* (µg/l)	MEC (µg/l)	RQ	MEC (µg/l)	RQ	MEC (µg/l)	RQ	
Fungicides								
Azoxystrobin	<i>0.2-1</i>	0.19	0.19 - Low	0.07	0.07 - Negligible	0.33	0.33 - Low	Rodrigues et al. 2017
Metalaxyl	<i>9.47- 20</i>	0.04	0.00 - Negligible					Carere et al. 2021
Tebuconazole	<i>0.24-1</i>	0.05	0.05 - Negligible	0.04	0.04 - Negligible	0.01	0.01 - Negligible	Stamatis et al. 2010
Thiabendazole	<i>3.3-1.2</i>	2.19	1.82 - Moderate	1.49	1.24 - Moderate	0.52	0.44 - Low	Pérez-Villanueva et al. 2022
Tricyclazole	<i>0.47-1.8</i>	0.01	0.01 - Negligible	0.01	0.01 - Negligible	0.03	0.02 - Low	Xie et al. 2020
Herbicides								
Diuron	<i>0.07-0.2</i>	0.04	0.21 - Low	0.02	0.11 - Low			García-Galán et al. 2020
Insecticides								
Carbaryl	<i>0.23-0.54</i>			0.23	0.42 - Low			Vryzas et al. 2011
Carbofuran	<i>0.016- 0.8</i>	0.29	0.36 - Low	0.12	0.15 - Low	0.06	0.08 - Negligible	Vryzas et al. 2011
Dimethoate	<i>0.07-4</i>			0.68	0.17 - Low			Vryzas et al. 2011
Imidacloprid	<i>0.013- 0.01</i>			0.08	8.30 - Moderate			García-Galán et al. 2020

1 **Figures (with their captions)**

2

3 **Fig. 1 a:** Location of the Tancat Mília and Tancat l'illa constructed wetlands within the *Albufera de*
 4 *València* Natural Park. The sampling sites within and outside each CW are indicated (orange dots are
 5 inner sites; blue dot is outer site). **b:** Scheme of the hydrological cycle of the *Albufera de València*
 6 Natural Park and the one-year rice cultivation cycle. The sampling dates of the study are indicated on the
 7 one-year cycle by means of red arrows

8 **Colour online only.**

9 **2-column fitting image.**

11 **Fig. 2** Seasonal means of heavy metal concentrations (all in $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) in the water within TLI and TM
 12 (ordered by concentration). The horizontal black line on each bar indicates the concentrations outside the
 13 CWs. (Aut: autumn 2020; Wi: winter 2021; ES: early spring 2021; LSp: late spring 2021; LSu: late
 14 summer). Thin vertical bars indicate standard error

15 **Colour online only.**

16 **2-column fitting image.**

17

18 **Fig. 3** Spatial and seasonal distribution of the presence of pesticides types (herbicides, fungicides and
 19 insecticides) within both CWs (a: TLI; b: TM) and outside. Compounds only found in one occasion have
 20 been not considered in this representation

21 **2-column fitting image.**

22

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24

25 **Fig. 4** Comparison of annual means of metal concentrations (all in $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) in the waters (sites grouped)
 26 within TLI and TM (a) and for sites outside the CWs (b). Statistically significant differences among
 27 element means between TLI and TM and between inside and outside the CWs (the arrows) are indicated
 28 by asterisks (*: $p < 0.05$; **: $p < 0.01$; ***: $p < 0.001$)

29 **2-column fitting image.**

30 **Colour online only.**